

Rethinking Public Participation: Including Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities

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Abstract Current public participation methods often fail to reach diverse communities, necessitating the development of more inclusive procedures. This research aims to improve municipal planning participation by focusing on citizens with intellectual disabilities, a traditionally underrepresented group. Existing open-source Web GIS platforms are made accessible for this target group, enabling their input into planning processes. By focusing on accessibility for individuals with disabilities, the project also aims to create tools that benefit the broader public, including those with low language proficiency or limited digital experience.

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1 Introduction

Municipal planning depends on the broad participation of the public as well as the responsible public authorities. Participation can open up relevant information about specific living environments, improve planning, and increase its acceptance. However, established frameworks for public participation have been criticized for only reaching articulate groups. To allow the broader public to provide input to municipal planning, it is important to not only empower the 'hard-to-reach', but also to rethink procedures that have been insufficiently adapted to different communities in society and are therefore difficult to access.

We report on work in progress in the project DiKomAll¹ (*Digitale Kommune für Alle*, engl. digital municipality for all), which brings together researchers from planning, special education, and geographic information science with citizens with so-called intellectual disabilities. Intellectual disability (ID) is identified by limitations in both intellectual functioning and adaptive behavior. The quality of life of people with ID is influenced by a complex interaction of personal and social environmental factors as described in the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) by the World Health Organization (WHO) [8].

The team explores how this group, which so far has little opportunity to provide input to municipal planning, can raise its needs and concerns through participatory processes, supported by geographic information tools [4]. The research is conducted in the context of two planning processes that are compulsory in Germany, namely the developments of the noise action plan (*Lärmaktionsplanung* [6]) and the municipal health plan (*Fachplan Gesundheit* [5]) in the city of Bochum. The latter is particularly relevant for the target group, as its purpose is to provide a data-driven basis for health-related decisions in all other municipal planning processes. Both plans make use of extensive databases and public participation. Initial experience with digital participation between the partners in the consortium shows that although this has reached some people in the city, it does not yet adequately represent the diverse communities in Bochum [3].

The aim of the project is to address two main research questions:

1. How can methods and systems be designed in a barrier-sensitive way based on the abilities and needs of people with so-called intellectual disabilities and physical limitations in order to make participation processes in municipal planning more accessible for various previously underrepresented communities using digital methods?
2. How can target group-relevant data, interrelationships of complex issues and municipal planning processes be identified, digitally prepared in a diversity-sensitive way and communicated so that they can be understood and used by diverse communities?

¹ <https://dikomall.github.io/website/>

2 Digital participation

The quest for equal participation of all people in municipal administration and politics is associated with the term inclusion and is called for as part of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities [7], but is rarely implemented so far. To address citizens with so-called intellectual disabilities, some of whom also have visual, hearing or mobility impairments, established methods and tools can be simplified and new methods developed. It is important to note that such accessible applications do not only benefit this specific target group; they make it easier for everyone to participate, e.g., people with low language proficiency or little digital experience. The developments for this specific target group therefore also benefit the general public.

In order to make the results readily available for municipalities to apply them, the project builds on existing open source software tools, namely KomMonitor² [2], OGITO³ [1], and KoboToolbox⁴. The former two are Web GIS platforms, as shown in Figures 1 and 2, but developed for succinctly different purposes. KomMonitor is an expert tool that provides indicator-based GIS and analysis tools directed at social planners. Municipalities use it to store and analyze socio-demographic data in small spatial units such as building blocks, acting as a social digital twin for municipal planning. The software is in productive use in a growing number of German municipalities, so that any new functionality reaches practitioners through a simple software update. OGITO, on the other hand, is a tool developed for data collection on map tables during public participation processes, therefore offering a much simpler user interface optimized for map table settings. Regarding those two tools, the main objective of the project is to explore to what extent they can be made accessible for the target group, enable the data flow from OGITO to KomMonitor to include input from participatory processes in analyses for municipal planning, and to test them in the context of the noise action plan and the health plan, respectively. KoboToolbox complements these map-centered tools with functionality for collecting ideas and feedback from the public on their own devices in a simple, intuitive interface.

3 Initial results

One year into this three year project, first results have been produced regarding the accessibility of digital participation tools in collaboration with the target group. A series of workshops has been conducted with representatives from the target group, who volunteered to act as co-researchers, test OGITO on a map table and provide feedback on its accessibility. It became clear early in the process that orientation on a map, including identifying personal points of interest (home, work, etc.) is

² <https://github.com/KomMonitor>

³ <https://github.com/52North/OGITO>

⁴ <https://github.com/kobotoolbox>

Fig. 1 Screenshot of the KomMonitor front end user interface.

Fig. 2 Screenshot of the OGITO front end user interface.

challenging for some users. While some users benefit from reduced complexity in visualizations, legends in plain speech, or highlighting subjectively relevant landmarks, map representations are less suitable for participatory processes for others. In these cases, frontal and ego perspectives serve as a bridge to support participation in map-based processes.

The group is currently experimenting with photo-based approaches, where input is collected in-situ by the users on their own smartphones. Overall, the collaboration with the co-researchers has shown that their disabilities are highly individual and

lead to different kinds of accessibility issues, so that one of the next steps will be to develop an approach that allows the tools to identify the simplifications and modifications that need to make to the user interface to make them accessible for a specific user. This work will be conducted in collaboration with usability experts.

Putting such an approach into practice will potentially require substantial modifications in the existing software implementations. It remains to be seen to what extent they can be implemented in the scope of the project. At this point, data collected in the public participation process that goes with the development of the noise action plan have been imported from KoboToolbox to the KomMonitor database through a custom data connector.

4 Conclusion and outlook

The potential to capture the perspectives of diverse and particularly underrepresented groups in public participation processes is currently underutilized because the tools and processes are not adaptable to the needs and capabilities of these groups. We have taken the first steps towards more inclusive public participation processes, which have shown a strong interconnection between the individual users' access barriers and the technical implementation of the tools. In the remainder of this project, we will focus on exploring the potential of individualized user interfaces that address a user's barriers and evaluate the extent to which this improves the participation of underrepresented groups.

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